

LAUDS FACTORIES

D 4.5 LAUDS Open Call outcomes and impact (round 1)

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Summary

Analyzing the OC#1 final reports, we derived here a semi-quantitative and qualitative analysis of the OC#1 performances and the efficiency of the LAUDS Factories framework. The development of the projects in terms of product maturity, communication and collaboration were satisfactory, the sustainability plans were not always convincing. While the projects reported positively from their experience, our analysis saw potentials in organizing a kick off event aiming at facilitating collaborations and planning and organizing expert coaching for technological and economical perspectives.

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1 Introduction

1.1 Goal of the report

We analyzed here the final reports of projects that were chosen for the first open call of the LAUDS Factories project (OC#1). The main objectives of this deliverable is to assess the success of the projects, as well as the efficiency of the support provided through the LAUDS Factories framework. This is meant to allow us to design a better support program for the second open call. To this end, we provided a semi-quantitative analysis of the performance of the OC#1 and of the support provided, and a qualitative analysis of the report on the topics of product development, sustainability measures, communication strategies and collaborative work. The analysis of collaborative work is structured across four layers: collaboration within OC#1 project teams, collaboration with LAUDS host factories, collaboration with LAUDS Factories researchers, and collaboration with local communities and networks. We finally analyze the feedback provided by the OC#1 team to the LAUDS Factories project. This report start by introducing each OC#1 project in the following introduction.

1.2 Limitations

This analysis relies primarily on self-reported project documentation produced by the project teams, which followed two templates we provided: one general report and one blueprint (Cangiano, S. (2025). Addressing the Data Gap in Urban Manufacturing: A Design-Driven Approach to Support the Scalability and Upskilling of NEB Innovations. *Innovations*, (HS1), 150–150. <https://doi.org/10.3917/inno.hs1.2025.0150>). As a result, the findings depend on the level of detail and transparency provided in the reports. Some indicators were coded at presence level only (e.g., different forms of support from LAUDS Factories) and therefore do not capture the intensity, frequency, or quality of collaboration and support. Consequently, the results should be interpreted as structured comparative insights rather than as evidence of causal relationships.

In addition, the formal nature of project reporting may encourage teams to present their activities and outcomes in a more positive light. For instance, one report mentioned that operating as a hybrid team working across disciplines posed challenges but did not elaborate on the specific issues encountered. As a result, some underlying difficulties or negative experiences may remain underreported.

1.3 Projects overview

The five projects funded through the Exploration Open Call address LAUDS challenges of agriculture and food production, circular material use, and energy and resource management. *Redesigning Gardens in the Air* and *Verdant Ascent: Inclusive Vertical 3D-Printed Garden for Communities* focus on vertical cultivation systems in urban environments, covering topics such as local food production, urban greening, and microclimate regulation. *The My(ne)stery of Matter*

– An Open Source Mobile Recycling Lab for the Masses looks at material reuse and local recycling practices, while *AERO: Energy-Saving Air Cleaner Made of Recycled Plastic for Operational Use* combines recycled material applications with air quality improvement solutions. *Human-Centric Energy Management System Design and Implementation* focuses on energy monitoring and management approaches adapted to makerspace environments, including aspects of energy transparency and efficiency. Overall, the projects cover areas related to sustainable manufacturing, resource circularity, and community-oriented technological applications.

Table 1: OC#1 project, host and challenge

Project ID & Title	Host	Challenge	Start Date	End Date
06 Redesigning Gardens in the Air	Maker	Agriculture/food production	20.11.2024	30.10.2025
14 The My(ne)stery of Matter	Maker	Energy	20.11.2024	19.08.2025
20 AERO	UL	Energy	20.11.2024	19.11.2025
40 Verdant Ascent	Maker	Agriculture/food production	01.12.2024	Still ongoing
43 Human-Centric EnMS	FCHH	Energy	19.05.2024	19.08.2025

1.3.1 The Redesigning Gardens in the Air Project

Many buildings in dense urban areas were not designed with energy efficiency or ecological integration in mind. This issue is more visible in disadvantaged neighborhoods, where opportunities for renovation are limited. At the same time, everyday activities generate underused resources such as air-conditioning condensate water and organic household waste, which have potential for small-scale environmental improvements.

The project Redesigning Gardens in the Air focuses on designing and testing a modular system that integrates organic waste treatment with urban food production. Building on the earlier Gardens in the Air initiative led by Nomad Garden (Seville), the project explores the reuse of condensate water and the closing of local material cycles. The system combines a

vermicomposting unit with an edible planter within a single module. Organic household waste is converted into humus using *Eisenia foetida* earthworms, and temperature stability under outdoor façade conditions is supported through porous ceramic containers and evaporative cooling using recovered condensate water.

The project was carried out by T11, Nomad Garden, Fab Lab Sevilla, and the community association Ecosistema 41 / AES Nuestra Señora de la Candelaria. T11 coordinated the project and produced the façade modules. Nomad Garden developed the worm system, plant components, and the educational framework. Fab Lab Sevilla provided engineering and digital fabrication support, including prototyping and adaptation of ceramic 3D printing. The community partner hosted the implementation site and involved educators, students, and residents in daily operation and maintenance, creating an active learning environment and ensuring continuous public engagement throughout the project.

1.3.2 The My(ne)stery of Matter Project

The project *My(ne)stery of Matter* addresses the growing global issue of textile waste, characterized by low recycling rates and increased consumption driven by fast fashion. The project focused on the development and testing of a mobile “Flying Lab” designed for decentralized textile waste processing. The initiative aims to enable local, small-scale approaches to collecting, sorting, and transforming textile waste outside centralized recycling infrastructures while raising public awareness of textile waste challenges.

The Flying Lab was equipped with open-source machines and set up as a mobile platform supporting hands-on experimentation with textile recovery and material transformation. Through iterative testing, the project explored the production of secondary materials such as yarns, insulation elements, and basic building components, while also piloting participatory formats such as textile swaps and workshop-based activities.

Implementation was carried out through a collaboration between fashion designer S. Prien and the interdisciplinary design studio HILO Textiles, working together as a joint team. Prien contributed design, artistic direction, and public engagement activities, while HILO Textiles led technological development, documentation, and workshop implementation. The project combined artistic, material, and technical approaches to prototype decentralized textile-processing methods.

My(ne)stery of Matter demonstrates the potential of mobile, community-embedded infrastructures to reframe textile waste as a resource and to support more sustainable, locally grounded material practices.

1.3.3 The AERO Project (Air Filtration for Small Workshops)

Small woodworking and craft workshops often operate in environments with poor air quality due to the accumulation of fine dust generated during sanding and cutting processes. Existing

filtration systems are frequently outdated, cumbersome, or financially inaccessible for small facilities, resulting in health risks for workers and inefficient dust-management practices.

The AERO project addresses these challenges by developing a compact and affordable air filtration machine tailored to the needs of small workshops. The system is designed to effectively capture fine wood particles while integrating recycled materials, particularly 3D-printed components produced from recycled plastic, to reduce environmental impact and production costs. Emphasis is placed on ergonomic use, energy efficiency, and seamless integration into existing workshop setups, providing a cleaner and healthier working environment without compromising usability or space.

The project was delivered by a multidisciplinary team combining engineering, design, and craft expertise. Nanotec Filter, led by engineer Damien Weber, contributed technical development based on extensive experience in air emission treatment. TE/AM Studio, represented by designer Théo Finck, provided product and industrial design to ensure that the machine meets functional, ergonomic, and aesthetic requirements. Together, the team integrated engineering solutions with user-centered design and practical insights gathered through direct collaboration with woodworkers and artisans.

1.3.4 The Verdant Ascent Project

Verdant Ascent is a modular vertical garden designed to promote sustainability and accessibility. Using 3D-printed components made from recycled PLA, the system supports low-waste production and encourages gardening as an inclusive activity for people of all abilities. The project aims to bring calming, nature-connected environments into semi-public indoor spaces such as offices, schools, and rehabilitation settings, offering an easy-to-install and maintain structure whose flexible configuration makes everyday interaction with greenery more accessible.

The system features a modular design that integrates an autonomous misting-based watering system and a closed-loop re-circulation setup that reduces the need for plumbing and simplifies maintenance. Its adaptable configuration supports both small and large layouts, and the adjustable height ensures that users, including wheelchair users and individuals with limited mobility, can reach and care for the plants with ease.

The project was developed through a collaboration between SuperForma, a 3D-printing studio working with sustainable materials, and Simone Fanciullacci Studio, a multidisciplinary design practice. The team contributed to design development, prototyping, material testing, and system configuration, reflecting their combined work across sustainable production, modular construction, and user-oriented considerations.

1.3.5 The Human-Centric Energy Management System Project

Energy Management System (EnMS) solutions are increasingly important for small manufacturing facilities, where energy monitoring and resource efficiency are often limited by cost, complexity, and the need for continuous human coordination. The Human-Centric Energy Management project focuses on the design and implementation of a modular EnMS that combines IoT devices, open-source software, and user-oriented interface design. The project addresses these challenges by developing an accessible, low-cost system that supports more reliable and transparent energy monitoring.

The system integrates seven monitored parameters, including energy use, filament type and usage, printer operating hours, nozzle and bed temperatures, vibration, and ambient conditions. Technical implementation is based on an open-source stack using Node-RED, Grafana, PostgreSQL/TimescaleDB, and Dockerized services, together with ESP32 hubs, smart plugs, and sensors.

Three user interfaces were developed: a technical interface, a simplified standard interface, and an artistic/awareness interface. The project followed an iterative process and resulted in an open-source demonstrator reaching TRL 6–7, suitable for use in real environments.

The project was delivered by a multidisciplinary team led by energy-management specialist Umut Ogur, with artistic and engagement components coordinated by Sebla Harnuboglu Ogur. Additional contributions from software, game design, and visual design members supported the integration of both technical and artistic dimensions. The resulting documentation provides a solid basis for replication and further development across Fab Labs and other urban manufacturing environments.

2 Method

2.1 Data Sources and research design overview

The analysis is based on official documentation submitted by the five OC#1 projects. Each project provided two reports: a *Production Process Blueprint* and a *Collaboration Report – Final Report*. In total, ten reports were reviewed.

This analysis applies a cross-project comparative approach, combining inductive qualitative content review (qualitative analysis) with descriptive quantitative aggregation (semi-quantitative analysis). In both cases, reports were used to create the framework of analysis, and the analysis was then performed using the framework in a second step. Due to the small sample size, the analysis focuses on identifying recurring patterns and variations, rather than establishing causal relationships or conducting inferential statistical testing.

2.2 Semi-quantitative analysis

All reports were systematically reviewed using an inductive and iterative process. Indicators were not predefined but developed progressively during the review. Segments referring to measurable outputs, reported support, collaboration-related activities, or feedback to LAUDS were extracted.

When all projects were analyzed, earlier cases were revisited to ensure consistency of categorization across all five projects. This process resulted in four analytical dimensions:

Table 2: Definition of Analytical Elements and Coding Approaches

Analytical Element	Definition	Coding Approach
Project Performance Indicator	Measurable activity or output reported by the project	Count- and Scale-based
Support – Local Host	Any support explicitly attributed to the hosting LAUDS factory	Yes / no
Support – Research Team	Any support attributed to LAUDS researchers or broader programme	Yes / no
Feedback / Suggestion	Explicit suggestion or reflection regarding program improvement	Qualitative summary

Performance indicators were operationalized using different measurement bases depending on the nature of the available information. Where numerical values were provided (number of workshops, deployment sites, media exposure, external visits), indicators were recorded as count data. In absence of indication, “NA” was indicated in the data. Where indicators reflected structured levels (Technology Readiness Levels), they were recorded using categorical scales. Support indicators were coded using a binary presence approach. Projects were coded as “Yes” if a specific support dimension was explicitly mentioned, or “NA” if no reference was identified in the documentation. “Not reported” indicates absence of documented evidence rather than confirmed absence of the activity. All indicators were compiled into a structured spreadsheet to enable systematic cross-project comparison.

Data analysis and visualization were performed using R statistical software and the ggplot2 package. The dataset and code are publicly available in the LAUDS Factories open data repository (Zenodo): <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13379044>

No inferential statistical analysis was conducted.

2.3 Qualitative analysis

In addition to numerical aggregation, a structured qualitative comparison was conducted. The results section of this document follows the structure of the Blueprint and Final Reports to maintain alignment with project documentation. The comparison is organized along key thematic areas, including product development and product maturity, exploitation and sustainability planning, communication and dissemination activities, collaboration patterns, and OC#1 team feedback to LAUDS Factories. Within each area, similarities and differences between projects were identified and synthesized to highlight recurring themes and variations in implementation.

3 Result

3.1 Semi-quantitative analysis

We first present information about the tools used at the LAUDS factories host. For the project outputs analysis, we first created a table of putative key outputs extracted iteratively during the OC#1 final reports analysis. In a second phase, we went through each report to code these key outputs in a spreadsheet. We created 3 different categories of outputs: performance indicators of the OC#1 project, support provided by the LAUDS Factories host, and support provided by the LAUDS Factories project members. This quantitative view of outputs and support will give an overview of the activities, while more details are included in the qualitative analysis which follows.

3.1.1 Fabrication Tools Used

Across the OC#1 projects, 3D printing and hand tools were the most frequently used fabrication technologies, appearing in four projects (see Table 3). Two of these projects relied on large-format 3D printing machines, while laser cutting was the second most commonly used fabrication technology. This pattern highlights the central role of 3D printing in the prototyping processes of the projects. It should be noted that the table includes only general fabrication tools, specialized equipment used for specific product development (e.g., digital microscopes, kilns, grinders) is not listed.

Table 3: OC#1 project use of manufacturing tools provided by the LAUDS Factories host

Project ID & Title	3D Printer	Hand Tools / Wood	Laser Cutter	Metal Tools	CNC Machine	Robotic Arm	Electronics workstation
06 Redesigning Gardens in the Air	✓	✓	✓			✓	
14 The My(ne)stery of Matter	✓	✓	✓	✓			
20 AERO	✓	✓		✓	✓		
40 Verdant Ascent	✓						
43 Human-Centric EnMS							✓

3.1.2 Project performance indicators

The project performance indicators present four kind of activities: design and manufacture work (number of models/variants, deployment site, local suppliers, putative customers), communication activities (media exposures, workshops, public presentations), collaborative work activities (number of visits), and planification activities after the LAUDS projects (Extension research). In Fig. 1, we depicted a quantification of these outputs. While these categories were not explicitly provided in the report template, most projects reported activities in all these domains (with only 12 missing values, and two "0" values, over the 45 points).

While AERO strikes out as an outliers with many more interactions with the host and a research for customers who would buy their machine, other projects had similar outputs focused primarily on community building activities. Most projects had several iteration of the design during the project. While we expected to measure the number of unit manufactured, the OC#1 project did not reach a stage of development allowing small scale production in the LAUDS Factories host.

Figure 1: Performance indicator of OC#1 projects.

3.1.3 Support reported

By collecting the support obtained, we provide here a quantification of the performance of the LAUDS Factories framework. Indeed LAUDS Factories provided support from the mentoring team at the host Maker, Fab- Cty Hamburg and Université de Lorraine (Fig. 2), as well as workshop and expert knowledge from the LAUDS Factories research teams (Fig. 3). It is important to note that the actual support was provided to all teams, but only some of them found it relevant enough to report it. We therefore interpret that the presence of the support in the report is an estimation of the quality of the support, even if the data was collected as a dichotomous variable (for each support, we analyzed whether it was present in the report, without trying to quantify its quality or relevance).

While the support provided was reported very positively, a specific support for planning the sustaining the project beyond the open call period was lacking both from the host and from the researchers. In addition, support for the communication strategy of the project was rarely reported, suggesting the communication strategy of the projects were only marginally modified nor enhanced by the support provided.

Figure 2: Support provided to OC#1 project from the LAUDS Factories host

Figure 3: OC#1 support provided by the Lauds Factories research teams

3.2 Qualitative analysis

This section presents a qualitative analysis of the OC#1 reports focusing on different aspects. This part of the deliverable follows the structure of the OC#1 reports. We first describe how the product matured during the project, then presents development toward sustainability, the communication outputs and how the collaboration worked.

3.2.1 Product development

Here we report on the development of the product during the OC#1 project. We first describe each case before presenting an overview of the maturation of the projects.

OC#1 products

- **Redesigning Gardens in the Air:** The team developed a modular vermicomposter system that integrates traditional fired ceramic pots "hacked" with custom components produced via 3D printing in PLA biocomposite. This climate-adaptive ecosystem utilizes water coming from air-conditioning systems for irrigation. It transforms organic residues into nutrient-rich humus, effectively closing local material loops.
- **Verdant Ascent:** This project produced an inclusive vertical 3D-printed garden characterized by a modular architecture composed of interlocking parts that can be assembled by hand. The internal aeroponic system features a submersible pump, adjustable push-in nozzles that atomize water into a fine mist, and a closed-loop water recirculation system to minimize water consumption.
- **The My(ne)stery of Matter:** The project implemented the "Flying Lab," a mobile lab designed to decentralize textile waste recovery and recycling. It manufactured three key open-source machines, the Macro Yarn Machine, Braiding Machine, and E-Spinner.
- **AERO:** The team developed a functional prototype of an industrial air cleaner (AERO) constructed from recycled plastic, which saves energy by releasing the hot air back inside the room. The machine is engineered for an air treatment capacity of 2,500 Nm³/h and achieves a filtration efficiency of 99.97% for fine particles smaller than 0.3 μm.
- **Human-Centric EnMS:** This project established a Human-Centric Energy Management System (EnMS), a modular digital solution that integrates custom ESP32-based sensor hubs to capture environmental and operational data. The system ingests data through Node-RED flows into a

PostgreSQL/TimescaleDB database, providing visualization via Grafana dashboards and an artistic interface to increase user engagement and resource awareness.

Product Maturity

Across the five projects, product maturity generally progressed from early concept stages (approximately TRL 3) to functional prototype validation stages (TRL 5–6). One project experienced delays, and real-world testing is still ongoing. The remaining four projects have completed testing and validation activities in real community environments or operational settings. It should be noted that only the project *Redesigning Gardens in the Air* explicitly defined its product maturity using the TRL framework. For the other projects, TRL levels were inferred based on the reported development stages and activities described in the project documentation.

Table 4: Maturation of hardware in OC#1 projects

Project ID & Title	TRL at start	TRL at the end
06 Redesigning Gardens in the Air	3	5-6
14 The My(ne)story of Matter	3-4	5-6
20 AERO	2	5
40 Verdant Ascent	2	4
43 Human-Centric EnMS	3	6-7

3.2.2 Exploitation and economic sustainability plans

Open-Source Strategy

All five projects reported the adoption of open-source dissemination practices in line with the LAUDS Factories program. Core development assets were made publicly accessible through platforms such as GitHub, GitLab, cloud repositories, or project-specific websites to support transparency, replicability, and further uptake. These outputs generally include hardware design documentation, manufacturing files, software and firmware components, as well as educational

or operational resources intended to facilitate reuse by other makers, organizations, or communities.

While the TUB team is still discussing with several projects about how licenses should be applied inside the documentation repositories, licensing approaches vary across the projects, ranging from fully open documentation and hardware licenses to hybrid models combining openly shared technical assets with service-based exploitation strategies (see Table 5). This diversity reflects different project needs, including safeguarding design integrity, supporting educational dissemination, or enabling future commercial sustainability. Links to version controlled repositories were indicated in the reports. We indicate here a list of links derived from the report or personal communication where links were not resolving: <https://github.com/jmlaulhe/LAUDS/tree/main>, <https://gitlab.com/StudioHILO/flying-lab> (machine is at <https://gitlab.com/StudioHILO/hilo-spinning-machine>), <https://hotmail539105.autodesk360.com/g/shares/SH90d2dQT28d5b6028115948475159a77e81>, <https://gitlab.fabcity.hamburg/lauds/lauds-factory-hamburg-ascent-verdant> (not accessible when writing this report), <https://gitlab.com/lauds/enms>.

Table 5: Summary of project documentation reusability as stated in the documentation itself, and not as stated in the OC#1 report.

Project ID & Title	Main Open Outputs	Access / Licensing Approach	Specific Notes & Constraints	Hosting Platform
06 Redesigning Gardens in the Air	Technical drawings, parametric design files, fabrication/assembly manuals, and educational recipes.	CC BY-SA (Docs) CERN OHL-W (Hardware)	Uses a dual-licensing strategy to cover both instructions and hardware processes.	GitHub, Zenodo, and Project Website
14 The My(ne)stery of Matter	Repositories for three recycling machines, machine and material usage guidelines, workshop manuals, and lab furniture designs	CC BY-SA (Docs) CERN OHL-W (Hardware)	Focuses on educational value; validated via remote replication by the host.	GitLab.com, Zenodo
20 AERO	Full 3D model (Fusion 360) including geometry, dimensions, materials, and assembly logic.	Closed source	Explicitly open for collaboration and sharing technical know-how.	Fusion 360 (protected Cloud Link)
40 Verdant Ascent	Printing files, slicing profiles, complete BOM, and "IKEA-style" instruction manual.	In discussion (CERN OHL-W)	Most restrictive: Prohibits commercial use and modifications to preserve design identity.	GitLab (Fab City Hamburg)
43 Human-Centric EnMS	Software codebase, firmware (esp.cpp), hardware specs, and artistic/visual assets.	In discussion, No license indicated	All core assets are open; team offers paid professional deployment and hardware kits.	GitLab.com

Exploitation Plan

Within this open-source framework, the projects present different exploitation strategies that vary in their degree of commercial orientation, ranging from education- and community-focused dissemination to more product-oriented market deployment. Redesigning Gardens in the Air and The My(ne)stery of Matter primarily emphasize educational and community-oriented approaches, focusing on training activities, workshops, and knowledge transfer rather than direct product commercialization. Verdant Ascent and Human-Centric Energy Management System Design and Implementation adopt combined product-and-service approaches, planning to develop deployable technical systems or modular products alongside services such as training, maintenance support, educational outreach, or system integration. AERO demonstrates

a clearer product commercialization orientation, focusing on the planned sale of industrial air filtration equipment with a potential future leasing model, indicating a more ordinary strategy towards market deployment.

3.2.3 Communication and Dissemination

Communication and dissemination activities across the five projects included workshops, public presentations, festival participation, media outputs, networking events, and community engagement activities (See Fig 1 and Table 6). These activities targeted a wide range of ecosystem actors, including maker communities, students, researchers, industry actors, local communities, and potential users, contributing to visibility of the projects beyond the immediate LAUDS ecosystem.

Beyond visibility, these activities also generated tangible follow-up effects in areas such as academic collaboration, market exploration, and longer-term institutional engagement. For example, Redesigning Gardens in the Air has been taken forward as a research topic within Aalborg University (AAU), under the supervision of Prof. Nicola Morelli, allowing further development of the concept beyond its original prototype context and within new research environments. For The My(ne)stery of Matter project, there was little development of the machines per se, but a major output of the project was the establishment of standardized material recycling recipes and workshop guidelines to enable communities to transform waste into new artifacts.

AERO adopted a dissemination approach with a stronger emphasis on on-site visits and direct engagement with industry actors. These activities contributed to the identification of potential market opportunities, with approximately 480 prospective clients identified and seven high-potential proposals currently under discussion, indicating early-stage pathways toward possible commercial deployment.

Table 6: Communication activities of OC#1 projects

Project ID & Dissemination Activities		Audience	Scale
Title	(By Category)		
06 Redesigning Gardens in the Air	<p>[Events] Public presentation (July 17) with "culinary ecosystem" tasting.</p> <p>[Workshops] 4 core workshops (Intro, Worms, Assembly, Podcasts).</p> <p>[Visits] 2 external visits to Seville urban gardens (incl. Tres mil Viviendas).</p> <p>[Media] 11-episode "Tierra Viva"</p>	AES Candelaria students, local gardeners, neighbors, university reps (US, UPO, UNIA), and AAU design students.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ~100 attendees at final demo. • 51 workshop participants (18 local + 37 AAU). • 50 reached in Seville / 50 in Copenhagen.

	podcast series.		
14 The My(ne)stery of Matter	<p>[Events] Major festivals: Roskilde (Circular Lab), Re:publica (Maker Space), Spor10</p> <p>[Workshops] 5 pilot workshops (Berlin Textile Coop, Spor10 Festival, Circular Lab, FGU Hovedstaden, Workshop part of Re:publica).</p> <p>[Talks] Speaking of: Textiles, Re:publica</p>	Festival goers, makers, textile designers, students, and local Copenhagen communities.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ~150 cumulative participants across all events.
20 AERO	<p>[Events] Public launch event; 17 days of professional networking events.</p> <p>[Visits] 25+ on-site visits to industrial companies and workshops</p>	SMEs, industrial groups, wood/metal workers, engineering/design schools, and Fab Labs.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 480 identified prospects. • 7 high-potential proposals in progress.
40 Verdant Ascent	<p>[Workshops] Month-long school installation and student collaboration (planned Jan 2026).<</p> <p>[Engagement] Local PLA recycling collection from schools and makers</p> <p>[Media] Social media updates on prototype progression.</p>	Middle school students, educators, local makers, and community facilities.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 1 local secondary school (month-long engagement)• Local community via material donation.
43 Human-Centric EnMS	<p>[Events] International showcase at Ars Electronica Festival (Linz).</p> <p>[Workshops] Interactive session at Fabulous St. Pauli (role-play, painting, 3D printing demo).</p> <p>[Media] 6 Instagram Reels by Arti Sanat.</p>	Maker communities, facility users, European researchers, artists, and DIY enthusiasts.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 30+ direct workshop participants. • 6,983 total Instagram Reel views. • 219 social media interactions

3.2.4 Collaborative work

Collaborative working is an essential aspect in the LAUDS Factories concept. We aimed at facilitating interactions inside OC teams, between OC teams and the LAUDS Factory host team, and between OC teams and local actors and communities. Here we analyzed how the collaborations were developed and how efficient they were at these different levels. The semi-quantitative data was not capturing much of these interactions (only the number of visits could be captured), and the report template for OC#2 should help capture these aspects better.

Collaboration inside OC#1 project teams

The projects were organized in hybrid team formats, bringing together designers, artists, engineers, and digital fabrication specialists from different professional backgrounds. Team expertise covered areas such as environmental science, mechanical engineering, digital manufacturing, service design, and social innovation.

Across the OC#1 projects, collaboration structures did not differ substantially despite the interdisciplinary composition of the teams. Most projects described their internal collaboration as iterative and co-creative, with responsibilities distributed among team members according to their areas of expertise. In one case, the report notes that these role boundaries became less rigid as the project progressed, with tasks and decisions increasingly shared across disciplines. Decision-making processes were generally described as collective, reflecting relatively horizontal structures. There was little use of workshops and hackathon formats. One team even reported that the planned hackathons strategy eventually evolved into a more continuous team-based working process.

Some coordination tools were also explicitly mentioned in the reports. For example, *AERO* used visual project management tools such as a whiteboard timeline and Miro (Gantt charts) to track progress. *Verdant Ascent* relied on structured planning tools provided by the LAUDS host, including Gantt plans and bill-of-materials (BOM) methodologies, to facilitate internal coordination. These tools were highlighted in the reports as supporting team collaboration and the organization of project work.

Collaboration with LAUDS Factories hosts

With the exception of *AERO*, OC#1 projects were not based close to the LAUDS Factory host and spend relatively little time on site. Collaboration therefore mainly relied on remote coordination, with physical interaction and use of host facilities typically took place at project kick-off, during testing and validation activities, or in connection with public engagement events.

In the case of *AERO*, the team was located in the same local area as the Green Fab Lab, at the heart of a third place (L'Octroi-Nancy) in which the Université de Lorraine is involved with the Lorraine Fab Living Lab, which fosters a continuum of innovation through a 2D-3D-4D process. This context enabled frequent and relatively informal interactions. This proximity facilitated regular in-person technical exchanges, including guidance on 3D printing processes, equipment maintenance, material selection, and fabrication methods, as well as ongoing feedback on prototype development. The host also provided access to equipment, troubleshooting assistance, and coordination support during the project.

Despite the geographic distance in most projects, LAUDS host organizations provided essential technical guidance, coordination support, and access to relevant networks (See also Figure 2). This included advice on materials, hardware, and fabrication processes, troubleshooting assistance, equipment maintenance support, training opportunities, and practical

recommendations that informed technical decisions and implementation approaches. Hosts also provided feedback on project direction and supported documentation and task organization. Beyond technical aspects, they facilitated connections with community partners, research organizations, industry actors, and other resident teams, enabling prototype testing in real environments, organization of public workshops, and engagement with potential users and stakeholders.

In some cases, production capacities of the host was not planned efficiently. This was particularly important for 3D printers, which were the most frequently used prototyping machines across the projects. Four out of five projects relied on 3D printing, two experienced delays due to printer malfunctions or insufficient printing capacity, which prevented the projects from progressing fully according to the initial plan.

Collaboration with LAUDS Factories researchers

Workshops organized within the LAUDS program addressed topics such as documentation practices, open-source licensing, and sustainability assessment approaches (See Figure 3). The interactions with the rest of the LAUDS Factories project were scarce but included a workshop on collaboration. While the OC#1 teams mostly felt the workshop was too far from the project, it might have helped with the internal collaboration. In addition Redesigning Gardens in the Air noted that workshops on open-source licensing and sustainability assessment “directly informed [their] documentation strategy.”

Collaboration with local communities and networks

Beyond direct host–project collaboration, the broader LAUDS hosts communities provided additional support through regular online exchange meetings, webinars, and workshops. These activities facilitated knowledge exchange, methodological guidance, technical input, and dissemination opportunities during the project period. For instance, AERO benefited from being embedded in a local multidisciplinary innovation environment, enabling interaction with nearby stakeholders and potential users. As described by the project team, the host organization and its Lorraine Smart Cities Living Lab “played a central coordinating role, allowing us to focus our energy on the core objective.”

Peer exchange across projects took place through online meetings and presentations, where teams shared experiences from parallel projects and discussed implementation approaches. Human-Centric Energy Management System Design and Implementation described the program as providing a collaborative framework that supported experimentation and exchange with other Open Call teams, while also offering additional visibility and dissemination channels.

3.3 OC#1 team Feedback to the LAUDS Factories project

OC#1 teams generally indicates positive experiences with the LAUDS Factories program, while also highlighting areas where future Open Call initiatives could be further strengthened. Host factories were widely recognized for providing access to fabrication facilities, technical advice,

coordination support, and opportunities for testing prototypes in real-world contexts. Their feedback contributed to the refinement of tools, systems, and implementation approaches. Program-level coordination and administrative support were likewise viewed positively, particularly regarding responsiveness to procedural and financial queries. Cross-project meetings and community exchanges were noted as valuable in fostering shared learning and increasing awareness of parallel developments across the Open Call projects.

At the same time, several operational and coordination challenges were identified. Collaboration across countries and multiple partner organizations required additional effort, particularly where logistical constraints, differences in digital working platforms, or cross-country fabrication processes were involved. In one case, prototype replication initially planned at host factories had to be reorganized due to limited 3D printing capacity, highlighting the technical and scheduling constraints that may arise when projects rely on specialized fabrication equipment. In addition, some challenges were related to program organization. Some online community sessions were perceived as lacking clearly defined objectives, which reduced their effectiveness. Certain training activities were also considered too general or insufficiently aligned with specific project needs.

3.3.1 Early-Stage Planning and Coordination

Several recommendations relate to the initial planning and coordination phase of future Open Calls. Organizing in-person kick-off events that bring together project teams and host factories could strengthen early alignment and collaboration. Clearer coordination mechanisms for cross-country manufacturing processes were also highlighted as important, particularly where fabrication complexity or long machine lead times are involved. Earlier and more structured technical exchanges between teams and host factories may help clarify environmental constraints, production capacities, and project expectations, thereby reducing uncertainty and supporting smoother planning.

3.3.2 Early Integration of Domain-Specific Expertise

Some feedback emphasized the value of involving specialized expertise earlier in project development. Engaging domain specialists – such as botanists, aeroponics experts, or other relevant technical professionals – during initial configuration stages may enhance project outcomes. Clearer guidance on accessibility and inclusive design was also identified as beneficial, particularly for projects involving interaction with vulnerable or diverse user groups.

3.3.3 Targeted Professional Advisory Support

Suggestions were also made for more specialized advisory support tailored to specific project needs. This could include guidance on funding strategies, certification pathways (for example circular design standards), and dissemination approaches for open hardware projects. Such targeted support may help projects navigate regulatory, financial, and communication challenges more effectively.

3.3.4 Peer Learning, Knowledge Exchange, and Visibility

Strengthening peer exchange mechanisms (communication between OC teams) emerged as another recurring theme. Suggested measures include the creation of a shared repositories where project documentation, datasets, and fabrication files can be indexed and cross-referenced. This would improve knowledge accessibility. To achieve greater visibility into other projects' activities it was suggested to create opportunities for local clustering of projects at shared host sites. Another recommendation concerns designing dissemination events that combine public presentation with active participation. Hands-on workshops could allow project outcomes to be experienced directly, increasing visibility while generating opportunities for constructive feedback.

3.3.5 Post-Project Continuity Mechanisms

Several recommendations focused on sustaining project outcomes beyond the funded period. These include establishing follow-up mechanisms or transition phases for projects reaching higher maturity levels, as well as providing micro-grants or access to public pilot program to support continuation, scaling, and real-world deployment.

4 Conclusions and lessons learned

In General, OC#1 team were successful in building advanced prototypes and validating them either in view of their commercialization, or in view of their use by communities. The support provided by the LAUDS Factories host and researchers was instrumental in this success. Through technical guidance, iterative feedback, and active support for networking and dissemination events, the hosts contributed significantly to the development process. In particular, the quality of the documentation produced is way above the quality of usual open source hardware projects. In most cases, the replicability of the prototypes was also tested and validated at the host factories, demonstrating their potential for distributed replication across community-based production environments.

For OC#2, the LAUDS Factories should better support the early stage of the project, making sure a kick-off event will facilitate both the collaboration in the OC team and the collaboration between OC teams and the host. Furthermore, production capacity at the host should be confirmed and planned at an early stage, especially for prototype replication, this may also

include the (economic) planning of support (material, services, machine usage, expert consultation, analytics / professional measurements) and logistics (accommodation, travel).

Early identification and involvement of experts for specific technologies could also help teams overcome technical bottlenecks more efficiently and explore technological possibilities. Additional support should be given to help to build better sustainability plans going beyond the OC project time. Similarly, the OC team could be helped with their online communication presence, leveraging the communication strategy of the LAUDS Factories project, including a social media strategy.

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